

Cult of Trophonius

also known as “Cult of Trophonios”

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Entry tags: Boeotia, Boeotian Religion, Hellenistic Religions, Greece, Religious Group, Greek Polis Religions, Ancient Mediterranean, Greek Cult, Greek Religions, Religious Place

This entry relates to the cult of Trophonius in the small city-state Lebadea in western Boeotia. Trophonius was a local oracular deity who was thought to be the son of either the Orchomenian hero Erginus or Apollo. He is credited with the building of Delphi with his mythical brother Agamedes (Homeric Hymn to Apollo 3.296). According to Pausanias (9.37.5-7), Trophonius and his brother built a treasury chamber for King Hyrieus on Boeotia, which included a secret entrance. The two brothers used this entrance to steal treasure from Hyrieus, who eventually realised that treasure was being taken from him and set a trap. Agamedes was caught in the trap, and Trophonius chopped off his brother's head so that he could not be recognised. Following this, he fled to Lebadea, where the earth swallowed him. Later, the Boeotians suffered from a two year drought and sent envoys from every city in the region to consult the oracle at Delphi, who told them that an unnamed hero was angry for not receiving cult. An envoy from the city of Acraephia found the cave of Trophonius after following a swarm of bees, and they began giving him cult - consequently, the drought ended, and Trophonius took his place as a local deity (Pausanias 9.40.1). Pausanias also recounts the process occurring when visiting the oracle, see 9.39.4. His significance can be seen in the story of Mys consulting Trophonius in the sixth century (Herodotus 8.133.1) and the message sent from Trophonius to the Thebans before the Battle of Leuctra in 371 BCE (Diodorus 15.53.4).

Date Range: 800 BCE - 200 CE

Region: Cave of Trophonius

Region tags: Greece, Boeotia, Lebadea

The cave of Trophonius in western Boeotia, near the sacred spring of the nymph Hercyna

Status of Participants:

✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

General Variables

Sources and Excavations

Print Sources

Print sources used for understanding this subject:

- Source 1: Schachter, A. (1994) *Cults of Boiotia: 3. Potnia to Zeus* [BICS Supplement], London: Institute of Classical Studies
- Source 2: Bonnechere, P. (2003) *Trophonios de Lébadée : cultes et mythes d'une cité béotienne au miroir de la mentalité antique*, Brill: Boston and Leiden
- Source 3: Bonnechere, P. (2002) 'Trophonius of Lebadea: Mystery aspects of an oracular cult in Boeotia'

in M. Cosmopoulos. ed. *Greek Mysteries: The Archaeology of Greek Secret Cults*, London and New York: Routledge, 169-192.

Reference: Schachter, Albert. *Cults of Boiotia Volume II: Herakles to Poseidon*. London: Bulletin for the Institute of Classical Studies Supplement, 1986.

Online Sources

Online sources used for understanding this subject:

- Source 1 URL: <http://www.perseus.tufts.edu/hopper/text?doc=Perseus:text:1999.01.0160:book=9:chapter=39&highlight=trophonius>
- Source 1 Description: Pausanias 9.39 - description of the temple and what happens at the oracle
- Source 2 URL: <http://www.perseus.tufts.edu/hopper/text?doc=Perseus:text:1999.01.0160:book=9:chapter=37&highlight=trophonius>
- Source 2 Description: Pausanias 9.37 - describes how Trophonius became a deity
- Source 3 URL: <https://www.theoi.com/Khthonios/Trophonios.html>
- Source 3 Description: Theoi entry for Trophonius as a deity.

Has this place been the focus of excavation (pre-modern, illicit, or scientific):

Answer 'Yes' for each period or type of excavation.

– Yes

Type of excavation:

– Scientific

Notes: The sanctuary was excavated in the late 1960's, but the main oracle location remains unidentified.

Years of excavation:

– Year range: The late 1960s

Name of excavation

– Official or descriptive name: Excavation of the sanctuary of Trophonius

Topographical Context

Is the place associated with a feature in the landscape

– Cave

Does the place involve human-made features besides structure:

Other features might be ground clearing, terracing, other modifications of the local environment.

– No

Is the place situated in an urban or significantly urbanized area:

– Yes

↳ Is there a distinct boundary between the place and the urban fabric:

– No

↳ Is the place located significantly within the urban fabric:

Is the place centrally located, or at the crossroads of significant pathways?

– No

Notes: The remains of the ancient cult is near the modern city of Levadia in western Boiotia and was near the ancient city as well.

Is the place situated in a rural setting:

– No

Is the place situated far removed from non-religious places of habitation:

– No

Structures Present

Are there structures or features present:

Instructions: Answer once for each structure/feature or group that can be differentiated.

– No

Notes: No structures of this temple survives, except some votive shelves in the hillside above the river Hercyna. In antiquity this sanctuary was in a cave, whilst the oracle was on top of a nearby mountain.

Reasons for Creation/Construction/Consecration

Is the place used for the worship of/communication with non-human supernatural beings:

– Yes

↳ Dedicated to a supernatural being:

– Yes [specify]: Trophonius as the main deity

↳ Dedicated to more than one supernatural being:

– Yes [specify]: Other deities present were Hercyna, Demeter Europe, Zeus Hyetios.

Is the place used for the worship of a semi-divine human being:

– Yes

↳ Is it a cenotaph:

– No

↳ Does it commemorate a family/clan/group:

– No

Is the place used for the worship of non-divine ancestors:

– Yes

↳ Is it a cenotaph:

– No

↳ Does it commemorate a family/clan/group:

– No

Was the place commissioned/built by an official political entity:

A political entity is a local power structure that leverages a workforce.

– Yes

↳ Specify

– Other [specify]: The sanctuary was within the territory of the polis Lebadea in Western Boeotia and may have been associated with the Minyan ethnic group through genealogical connections between Trophonius and the Minyan hero Erginnus. The alternative link to Apollo provides a stronger link to the Boeotians, as the cult of Trophonius fits with a typical Boeotian cult type of Apollo, see Schachter (1967). According to the tradition as recounted by Pausanias, it was the Boeotians as a regional group who founded the cult of Trophonius, see Pausanias 9.40.1.

Were the Structures built by specific groups of people:

– Yes

↳ Groups:

– Other [specify]: The local population in Lebadea

Was the place thought to have originated as the result of divine intervention:

– No

Notes: Although in the tradition recounted by Pausanias it is implied that a swarm of bees led the Boeotians to find the cult site.

Was the place created to mark or commemorate the birthplace of a supernatural or human being:

– No

Notes: Instead, it was where the earth swallowed Trophonius as he fled king Hyrieus' wrath after stealing the king's treasure.

Was the place created as the result of an event:

– Yes

↳ Specify

– Other [specify]: According to the tradition the earth swallowed Trophonius at this location as he was fleeing from King Hyrieus. Many years later the Boeotians suffered a drought and asked the Pythia for help to find a way to stop the drought. They were advised that a unnamed hero or deity was angry and that they needed to find his grave and begin worshipping him. After several failed attempt a representative from Acraephia followed some bees into a cave, where he found Trophonius. Through this the sanctuary was set up as a result of this mythical event.

Was the creation of the place sponsored by an external financial/material donation:

– I don't know

Was the establishment of the place motivated by:

– Other [specify]: The establishment was according to the tradition to end the mythical drought - when the envoy found Trophonius the drought ended, and the sanctuary was founded as a very popular oracular sanctuary.

Was the place built specifically for housing scriptures/sacred texts:

– No

Design and Material Remains

Overall Structure

Is the place made up of multiple built structures:

– No

Is monumental architecture present:

Monumental architecture is defined here as a built structure that surpasses average human proportions and in general is larger and more complex than is necessary to fulfill the structure's utilitarian function(s). Examples of monumental architecture include Mesopotamian Ziggurats, Egyptian Pyramids, Greek and Roman temples, Mesoamerican Pyramids, North American and Aegean burial mounds, etc.

– No

Notes: The sanctuary of Trophonius was a cave sanctuary.

Is the structure/feature made out of natural materials:

Answer [Yes] for each material type

– Yes

↳ Earth

– Yes

↳ Is this material sourced locally:

– Yes

↳ Is this material lacking in the local natural environment:

– No

↳ Sand

– No

↳ Clay

– No

↳ Plaster

– No

↳ Wood

– I don't know

↳ Grass

– No

↳ Stone

– Yes

|

↳ Is this material sourced locally:

– Yes

Notes: The natural rock in the local mountain

↳ Is this material lacking in the local natural environment:

– No

↳ Other

– Other [specify]: The structure of the sanctuary is was within a cave. There it was made using a natural feature in the landscape around Lebadea.

Is the structure/feature made out of human-made materials

– No

Decoration

Is decoration present:

– No

Iconography

Are there distinct features in the places iconography:

– Yes

↳ Eyes (stylized or not)

– Yes

↳ Supernatural beings (zoomorphic)

– Field doesn't know

Notes: Although there were snakes included in the iconograph at the sanctuary as described by Pausanias 9.38.3-4. These were around staffs of the statues at the sanctuary.

↳ Supernatural beings (geomorphic)

– No

↳ Supernatural beings (anthropomorphic)

– Yes

- ↳ Supernatural beings (abstract)
 - No
- ↳ Portrayals of afterlife
 - No
- ↳ Aspects of doctrine (e.g. cross, trinity, Mithraic symbols)
 - No
- ↳ Humans
 - No
- ↳ Supernatural narratives
 - No
- ↳ Human narratives
 - No
- ↳ Other [Specify]
 - Other [specify]: N/A

Beliefs and Practices

Funerary Associations

Is this place a tomb/burial:

– No

Notes: Although it was the location where Trophonius as a mortal hero had been swallowed by the earth. A part of the cave was also reserved for Agamdes, the brother of Trophonius, Pausanias 9.39.6..

Is this a place for the worship of the dead:

– No

Is this a place for treatment of the corpse:

– No

Are co-sacrifices present in tomb/burial:

Co-sacrifices are animal/human sacrifices prompted by the death of the primary occupant of the tomb/burial.

– No

Are grave goods present:

– No

Are formal burials present:

– No

Supernatural Beings

Is a supreme high god is present:

– Yes

Notes: As the sanctuary was dedicated to Trophonius, he was the supreme deity of the sanctuary. In two periods he was associated with Zeus, the supreme deity in the Hellenic pantheon, see Schachter (1994) 76, see also Husøy (2021) 77.

↳ Are they anthropomorphic:

– Yes

↳ Are they sky deity:

– No

↳ Are they chthonic (underworld)

– Yes

↳ Are they fused with king/kingship role (king = high god)

– No

↳ Are they the monarch is seen as a manifestation or emanation of the high god:

– No

↳ Are they kin relation to elites:

– No

↳ Are they other type of loyalty or connection to elites:

– No

↳ Are they unquestionably good:

– No

↳ Are they other:

–Other [specify]: N/A

Does the supreme high god communicate with the living at this place:

– No

Notes: Trophonius as a prophetic deity communicated with the living in this place. The process is recorded by Pausanias i 9.39.4, who also states that he completed the ritual himself, see also Pretzler (2007) 42.

Are previously human spirits present:

– Yes

↳ Human spirits can be seen:

– No

↳ Human spirits can be physically felt:

– No

Do human spirits communicate with the living at this place:

– Yes

Notes: Through oracular prophecies.

↳ In waking, everyday life:

– Field doesn't know

↳ In dreams:

– No

↳ In trance possession:

– No

↳ Through divination practices:

– No

↳ Only through religious specialists:

– No

↳ Only through monarch:

– No

↳ Other

–Other [specify]: N/A

Are nonhuman supernatural beings present:

– Yes

↳ Nonhuman spirits can be seen:

– No

↳ Nonhuman spirits can be physically felt:

– Yes

Do nonhuman spirits communicate with the living at this place:

– Yes

↳ In waking, everyday life:

– Yes

↳ In dreams:

– I don't know

↳ In trance possession:

– No

↳ Through divination practices:

– Yes

↳ Only through religious specialists:

– No

↳ Only through monarch:

– No

↳ Other

–Other [specify]: N/A

Are mixed human-divine beings present:

– Yes

Notes: By mixed human-divine being I am here meaning human heroes which became deities, two of which were represented at this sanctuary, namely Trophonius (the main deity at the sanctuary) and Agamedes.

↳ Mixed human-divine spirits can be seen:

– No

↳ Mixed human-divine spirits can be physically felt:

– Yes

Do mixed human-divine beings communicate with the living at this place:

– No

Is the supernatural being/high god present in the form of a cult statue(s):

– Yes

↳ Is the cult statue visible:

– Yes

Notes: It was in antiquity, but unfortunately it is now lost. According to Pausanias the icons of Trophonius and Hercyna was similar to statues of Asclepius and Hygeia due to some the use of serpents in the iconography - serpents were sacred to both Trophonius and Asclepius. See also Aston (2004). There was also an statue of Trophonius made by Praxiteles.

↳ Is the cult statue hidden:

– No

Supernatural Interactions

Is supernatural monitoring present:

– Field doesn't know

Do visitors communicate with the gods or supernatural beings:

– Yes

↳ Do visitors communicate with gods:

– Yes

↳ Do visitors communicate with other supernatural beings:

– Yes

Ritual and Performance

Do rituals occur at this place:

Rituals are visibly enacted behaviors by one or more people for the purposes of religious observance.

– Yes

↳ Do large-scale rituals take place:

– Field doesn't know

Notes: Yet, the Trophonion festival may be considered such a large scale ritual.

↳ Do small-scale rituals take place:

– Yes

Notes: Small scale rituals for individuals wishing to consult Trophonius.

↳ On average how many participants are present in large-scale rituals:

–specify: Unknown

↳ How often do these rituals take place:

–specify: Unknown

↳ Are there orthodoxy checks:

– No

Notes: Yet, there is a set list of rituals and steps to consult Trophonius.

↳ Are there orthopraxy checks:

– Field doesn't know

↳ Are there synchronic practices:

– Yes

↳ Are there intoxicants used during the ritual:

– Yes

Notes: This is implied by Pausanias, as he states that "They call these boys Hermai: they wash the man who is going down and act as his servants, like slave boys. From here he is taken by the priests not straight to the oracle, but to the underwater springs, which are very close together. Here he must drink from the water of Forgetfulness, to forget everything in his mind until then, and then the water of memory, by which he remembers the sight he sees in his descent", Pausanias 9.39 (translation by Peter Levi in the Penguin Classics volumes).

Sacrifices, Offerings, and Maintenance

Are sacrifices performed at this place:

– Yes

↳ Are there animal sacrifices:

– Yes [specify]: According to Pausanias (9.39.3), meat was often sacrificed for Trophonius as well as his children, Apollo, Cronos, Zeus Basileus, Hera, and Demeter Europa. Before descending into the cave the inquirer sacrifices a ram to Agamedes to invoke this hero.

↳ Are there human sacrifices:

– No

↳ Are the sacrificed humans associated in some way:

– No

Are there self-sacrifices present:

– Field doesn't know

Are material offerings present:

– I don't know

Is attendance to worship/sacrifice mandatory:

– No

Is maintenance of the place performed:

– Yes

↳ Is it required:

– No

Notes: Yet, maintenance surely was a part of the local upkeep of the sanctuary.

↳ Is there cleansing (for the maintenance):

– No

↳ Are there periodic repairs/reconstructions:

– Yes

↳ Is the maintenance performed by permanent staff:

– No

↳ Other

–Other [specify]: N/A

Pilgrimage and Festivals

Are pilgrimages present:

– No

Is this place a venue for feasting:

– No

Are festivals present:

– Yes

↳ Frequency of festivals

–specify: Unknown, the festival is only attested twice in the second century BCE

↳ Do all members of the society participate in the festival(s):

–All members

Notes: Grigsby suggests that the festival was a local reorganisation of the federal Basileia festival which was no longer celebrated in the time when the Trophoneia was celebrated

(Grigsby, P. [2017] 142). The festival had wide-ranging participation as shown by Athenians and Megarians attending the athletic competitions.

↳ Are festivals a defining element in the construction/decoration of the place:

– No

↳ On average, how many participants gather at this place:

– number: Unknown

↳ Is feasting part of the festival(s):

– Field doesn't know

Divination and Healing

Is divination present:

– Yes

↳ Divination by examination of the exta:

Animals remains, internal organs, answer this question and subsequent question once for each species

– No

↳ Divination through human communication:

– No

↳ Divination through animal-behavior:

– No

↳ Divination through non-living material:

– Other [specify in comments]

Notes: N/A

↳ Other

– Other [specify]: See Pausanias 9.39.

Institutions and Scriptures

Religious Specialists

Are religious specialists present/in charge of this place:

Religious specialists are individuals who's primary duties within a population group are not concerned with subsistence or craft production but the maintenance of the religious landscape and culture of the group.

– Yes

Present full time

– Field doesn't know

Present part time

– Field doesn't know

Are the religious specialists of specific sex/gender:

– Field doesn't know

Are the religious specialists of specific ethnicity:

– Yes

Notes: The priest would have been Hellenes, as a part of the regional ethnic group of the Boeotians as well as the city-ethnic of the Lebadeans.

Are the religious specialists of specific class/cast:

– No

Notes: Although the Hermai who is a part of the ritual acted as servant boys to the people who undertook the ritual.

Are religious specialists dedicated to the place for life:

– Field doesn't know

Are the religious specialists stratified in a hierarchical system:

– Yes

Is access within the space segregated by this hierarchy:

– Field doesn't know

Bureaucracy

Is there a formal bureaucracy present at this place:

A bureaucracy consists of a hierarchical system of accounting and rule maintenance primarily concerned with material wealth.

– I don't know

Does this place control economic resources (land, goods, tools):

– I don't know

Public Works

Does this place serve as a location for services to the community:

– Yes

↳ Public food distribution and/or storage:

– No

↳ Place for civic functions (census, elections, others):

– No

↳ Place for the practice of justice (trials, executions, etc.):

– No

↳ Function for water management:

– No

↳ Part of the transportation network:

– No

↳ Other

–Other [specify]: N/A

Writing/Scriptures

Is non-religious writing stored at this place:

Economic documents, records etc.

– No

Are there scriptures associated with this place:

– No

Bibliography

General References

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Entry/Answer References

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